

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL STUDIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of the study and research of scientific fields. Specifically, it evaluates methodological approaches to the study of the history of Uzbekistan in the 20th century, examining issues related to biased views on historical science and the falsification of history. It also analyzes approaches to the development of historical science during the years of independence, which have resulted in attempts to objectively study and create a history of the Motherland and advances relevant ideas.*

Keywords: *methodology, formational approach, civilizational approach, science, ideological views, development.*

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that the modern world is developing based on fierce competition at every stage and in all fields. This extremely intense and fierce competition can only be countered by strong scientific potential, scientific achievements, innovative technologies, and their results in production and application in the social sphere.

Modern development poses a serious challenge for every state and nation: the development of fundamental and applied sciences in order to protect national interests and further strengthen the intellectual potential of society. "Developed countries around the world," says President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "set themselves the goal of not only increasing production and bringing it to market, but also transitioning to an innovative economy based on deep knowledge and scientific achievements. That is, developing their economies not by squandering existing natural resources, but by creating and developing innovative products and introducing advanced technologies into production is becoming the primary driver of development" [1, p. 235].

At the current stage of social development, the role of science in ensuring a country's economic strength, political influence, and social diversity is becoming increasingly important. Rapidly advancing globalization and the rapid advancement of digital technologies and artificial intelligence associated with the Fourth Industrial Revolution pose enormous challenges for all sciences and fields of science, including the social sciences and humanities.

The reasons for this are, firstly, related to the policies of developed and advanced countries aimed at strengthening their dominance over other states, regions, and peoples in pursuit of their national interests. Secondly, they are directly consistent with changes occurring in the modern world, with the growing "improvement" of the spiritual and ideological worldview and the devaluation of ancient values.

It has been extensively argued that under such conditions, the role and influence of the social sciences and humanities are increasing. In this context, it is necessary to express some considerations regarding the methodological and theoretical foundations of studying the social

sciences and humanities. For example, in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," "methodology" is a Greek word defined as the science of learning, the scientific method, and the methods of individual sciences. "Method" is interpreted as a research method, a path, a way of understanding and studying natural and social phenomena [2, p. 583].

It should be noted that there is still no single, unified concept recognized by all researchers in the field of methodology. Although researchers pay attention to methodological issues in scientific research, almost all of them strive to select methods that are specifically suited to their study of natural and social phenomena, including historical events.

In our opinion, the theoretical conclusions presented in the "Encyclopedia of World Philosophy" on the issue of "methodology" can be considered to have a certain commonality. In particular, it is noted that "methodology" is 1) a set of research methods applied in a specific discipline; 2) a science, a study of methods. The concept of methodology has two main meanings: a system of specific methods used in an activity (in science, politics, culture, and art); and a study of a system or theory of methods. Methodology is also a field of scientific research that studies a set of methods and a type of activity. Methodology studies not only methods but also other means of supporting research. Such means include principles, rules, and instructions, as well as categories and concepts [3, p. 788].

While each individual science has its own research methodology, it is also necessary to consider the existence of concepts common to all scientific fields. Specifically, methodology is understood as a philosophical doctrine of principles that must be understood and taken into account when setting goals, finding solutions, conducting activities in various areas of life, as well as predicting, determining, and evaluating the results and consequences that accompany all of this.

At the same time, each study must have its own methodology for collecting, processing, analyzing, and summarizing primary data. In this sense, the method consists of setting a specific goal, defining objectives based on this goal, and finding ways to achieve them. As in all fields, it is necessary to define a system of principles essential to conducting scientific research in the field of history. This is necessary for defining the object and subject of the science, for the ability to look back on the past as a result of the research, for examining connections and interrelations, determining their significance, and for expanding the scope of application of the research results [4, p. 416].

During the years of independence, a certain focus was placed on the honest study of the methodology of the social and human sciences, particularly history, based on the principles of scientific rigor, impartiality, and accuracy. This allowed us to accurately apply the specific perspectives on the social and human sciences, particularly history, that had developed during the Soviet dictatorship.

In this context, it's important to note some considerations regarding the negative attitude toward science, especially history, during the Soviet dictatorship, such as the falsification of history and the deification of certain issues. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasizing the enormous role of history in national development and the education of youth in the spirit of boundless love for the Motherland, notes that the further development of this science seriously lags behind modern requirements. He emphasized that, although many years have passed since we gained national independence, even now, "scientific research on history is conducted primarily in a descriptive and journalistic manner. As a result, the essence of many events in our distant and recent past, the factors that caused them, and the laws of history remain unexplained. We all need to deeply understand one truth: national history must be transmitted to our people, especially our

youth, in the national spirit and must be ingrained in their hearts and minds. Otherwise, it will have no educational effect.

It is well known that our people have experienced many unforgettable events, both periods of victory and tragic days, throughout their ancient history. However, one truth must be emphasized: every state system, every social process that has existed on the territory of our homeland – be it victory or defeat, rise or decline – is the work of our people. It is an integral and inseparable part of the complex historical path we have traversed. That is why we must perceive all stages of our history as a whole and study them thoroughly from all angles [1, p. 275].

It is commonly assumed that current stage of social development, attention to our national history has begun to improve in a certain direction. This creates the opportunity to study topics that were once urgently needed but were forbidden. As a result of examining history as an example, a broad and comprehensive study of all periods and all scientific issues of our national history has begun, based on the principles of justice and science. One such scientific issue is the study of the history of science, which is an important aspect of our national history, particularly in higher education. However, before examining the current state of this scientific problem, we consider it important to reflect on its status during the Soviet dictatorship.

In the study of our national history, including the history of science, the work of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, entitled "No Future Without Historical Memory," undoubtedly has significant theoretical and methodological significance. First of all, it is necessary to consider his reflections on science. "In general," says Islam Karimov, "I perceive science in the same way as the words progress, development, and advancement. I understand that the task of science is to determine the shape and direction of our future, to show where tomorrow will take us, the laws of nature, and what it will be like. It is necessary to prove and explain to people the advantages of independence, that a nation without independence has no future, that this is a law of nature. Science must be a force, a means of advancing the development of society" [5, p. 25].

The author notes in his work that the history of Uzbekistan in the full sense of the word was not actually created, and this was due to the political and ideological goals of Soviet ideology. Indeed, it can be said that the Soviet period, which lasted 74 years, was primarily a period of "experiments" in culture and education. It is well known that each stage in the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan, and in particular the history of the Uzbek people, is characterized in its own way: on the one hand, by unprecedented development in the socio-political, economic, spiritual, and ideological spheres, and on the other, by serious losses in these areas. These changes became especially dramatic due to the October Revolution. The October Revolution artificially blocked the ancient Eastern method of human development, almost halting it due to open discrimination. At the same time, the Eastern path had its own unique world. It was also distinguished by its important place in civilization, the existence of social justice, a political culture, unique democratic rules, and the prevalence of national and universal harmony in socio-cultural life.

It should be noted that the post-1917 period intensified the policy of distorting and falsifying the spiritual life and educational system of the Uzbek people, which had been shaped over millennia in the country's national history. One such example was the unification under the false banner of denying the deep roots of Eastern peoples, particularly Uzbek culture and education, and the elevation of peoples doomed to colonialism to the level of world civilization with the help of the invaders in order to strengthen their own political influence. The

disparagement of the educational system established in our country and the accusation of its one-sided development, particularly from a religious perspective, subsequently reached the level of public opinion in Uzbekistan. Political games, deception, and often direct pressure also led to a change of heart among some national intellectuals with weak faith. The October Revolution and its aftermath in Uzbekistan brought about significant changes in all aspects of the social sphere. On the one hand, the Bolsheviks, through the active introduction of class, ideological, and party principles into culture and education, embarked on the path of Sovietization and politicization of all public life. On the other hand, "Proletkultists" and "Ropovists" emerged under the banner of a "new," "separate" public life.

During this period, spiritual life was built on the foundation of a relentless struggle between the Bolshevik "new" and the local and national "old." To achieve this goal, from the very first days of the establishment of the Soviet regime, the Bolshevik Party pursued a policy aimed at ensuring its transformation into the sole, dominant party, combating all theories and ideas alien to its policies and eliminating their influence. The Soviet state's efforts to eradicate illiteracy among the population of Turkestan, build schools, develop higher education, and train specialists were aimed not at the interests of the local population, but rather at re-educating the country's population in the "communist spirit" and shaping them into "worthy" socialist specialists through cultural and educational means. The goal was to eradicate illiteracy among the population of all ages and teach them the "alphabet of communism."

The above-mentioned considerations and thoughts indicate that Soviet-era ideology, by every means possible, accused the population of illiteracy and lagging behind world civilization, and as a result, led them to new stages of development. Moreover, this ideological perspective dominated all works produced during the Soviet dictatorship. Attempts were made by every means possible to Sovietize the local population and instill in them all the elements of communist ideology.

It has been well documented that almost all works created at that time deified Soviet ideology, while our own path to national development, shaped over millennia, was denigrated. "The above considerations naturally raise the following question," says the First President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, "have we created a true history of Uzbekistan and the Uzbek people today, one worthy of being shared with the general public? I do not consider history written during the Soviet era to be history. I am categorically opposed to teaching history written by others. When did the colonizers ever express an honest, fair opinion of the people they subjugated? They expended all their energy on belittling Turkestan's past, on depriving us of our history. You probably know very well what it means to be deprived of history. For a person, to be deprived of history means to be deprived of life" [5, p. 10].

The 1920s and 1930s were an extremely difficult period, and despite the dominance of Bolshevik ideology, the national intelligentsia strove to demonstrate its abilities in all areas of science, education, and culture. This was especially true of science and education, which were important factors in changing people's minds. In the early years, certain democratic principles existed to a certain extent in the social sphere, particularly in the management of science and education, and the authorities were forced to take into account local customs and peculiarities. Later, as administrative-command methods spread and consolidated, the pursuit of common indicators, the Bolshevik path, and the methods of the "cultural revolution" became dominant. In this area, the formation of new cadres and the elimination of the old national intelligentsia were carried out with these goals in mind. The increase in literacy, the strengthening of the bureaucratic

system of governance, the transition to technical development, and the creation of scientific institutes occurred simultaneously with the establishment of strict ideological control over them [6, p. 243].

Although the process of ideologizing the social and humanities spheres and instilling the "advantages" of pseudo-socialism into the public consciousness intensified throughout the Soviet era, the 1980s became particularly acute in this regard. In particular, contradictory situations in science and education intensified.

There were several reasons for this. Firstly, by this time, the Soviet state had begun to lose all its potential. Extensive development was no longer viable, and the closed nature of the Soviet state and the lack of strong integration with the world prevented the use of intensive approaches. On the other hand, the primary goal in science and education was to satisfy the economic and material interests of the former center. Therefore, by any means necessary, the primary focus was on extracting as much material goods and wealth as possible from the national republics, including Uzbekistan. The priorities of science, including the higher education system, in scientific fields were determined by the extent and speed with which the former central needs of this field could be met.

On the other hand, the position of the social sciences and humanities in the higher education system had become even more pressing by this time. Soviet ideology and the ideological foundation of the system were unable to cope with the global competition of the time. Therefore, the social sciences and humanities were required to even more clearly demonstrate the "advantages" of the Soviet system, proving by any means necessary that socialism was the most just and humane state in the world. Scholars and specialists labored to disprove these false ideas. As a result, the resulting "works" found no place in the public sphere, and the general public rejected them.

As a result, the "advantages" of socialism, new methods and ways of conducting social and spiritual life began to be deified. During the "reconstruction" period, scholars and specialists were granted a certain degree of scientific and creative freedom, and initiative was permitted. Although it seemed possible to address previously impossible, "closed" topics, ideological certainty prevented such work from being carried out in practice. However, the bold efforts of leading intellectuals, scientists, and academics were viewed as hostile to the Soviet regime. Another reason for this was the form-building approach to assessing historical events, which developed during the Soviet era and fundamentally contradicted the development of the scientific field, especially research in the interests of the state, making it a methodologically flawed approach.

The process of scientific research reveals that in the study of historical processes, there exist civilizational and form-building approaches. The form-building approach achieved a dominant position in Soviet history under Marxism-Leninism. It stems from the category of "socio-economic formation"—the type of society at a particular stage of development. According to this doctrine, the material factor in the development of society is material production. The mode of production includes productive forces and production relations. The material life of society is primary, and social thought is secondary.

According to proponents of this approach, Marxist-Leninist doctrine is the key to understanding the unity and diversity of human history. The successive succession of social formations constitutes the main direction of human development. The transition from one socio-economic formation to another occurs through social revolutions. The emergence of a new formation is determined by the victory of the ruling class, which carries out revolution in all

spheres of life. Marxist theory places particular emphasis on revolution and class struggle. The primary driving force of history is class struggle [7, p. 57].

It should be remembered that the formalist approach to the study, analysis, and scientific, truthful conclusions about historical processes played a negative role in our national history. The most regrettable aspects of this approach were that it relegated the individual, the subject of history, to a secondary place and generally downplayed the role of the spiritual factor. Another regrettable aspect of this approach was its emphasis on the role of revolutionary situations and violence in historical processes. All this ultimately led to the development of scientific fields in Uzbekistan, including the higher education system, in a manner that denied national identity, even to the point of denying the past culture, educational system, and national-cultural and scientific heritage created by Central Asian thinkers and scholars. The formative approach created an atmosphere of suppression of our national intelligentsia and the glorification of scientists, primarily of the Soviet era.

In historical science, the civilizational approach, in turn, contradicts the formative approach. It should be emphasized that the civilizational approach to historical processes is considered to have emerged in the 18th century, primarily in Europe. However, it should not be forgotten that the civilizational approach was developed much earlier in the East, in particular by Ibn Khaldun (1332-1402). Abdurrahman ibn Muhammad ibn Muhammad Abu Zayd ibn Khaldun first presented a systematic view of civilization in his multi-volume work "Muqaddima." The author calls "civilization" "umran." He believes that the inner meaning of history involves reasoning and the pursuit of truth, requiring a subtle analysis of the causes and origins of existing things, as well as a profound study of how and why events occurred. Ibn Khaldun also emphasizes the absolute impossibility of taking sides in the study of history. Taking sides and displaying a particular bias blinds insight, weakens critical judgment, and hinders research. As a result, false information is accepted and disseminated.

The author understands history as a narrative about human society, which by its very nature is considered a world civilization. Warning historians, Ibn Khaldun writes: "If a historian accepts information directly and is unaware of the ordinary laws of those historical situations, the rules of politics, the nature of civilizations, or the circumstances that determine the reality of human society, and does not compare distant or ancient information with recent or contemporary information, then it is quite likely that he will encounter errors" [8, p. 61].

The advantages of the civilizational approach to the study of historical events lie in the fact that its principles can be applied to any state or group of societies. It does not deny, but rather affirms, the unity and integrity of human history, takes into account the contribution of each people to world civilization, and emphasizes the importance of moral, spiritual, and intellectual factors in historical processes. As noted by prominent scholars S. Shodmonova and M. Yuldashev, the civilizational approach to historical processes is the study of a holistic social system that unites various interconnected elements (religion, culture, economics, politics, and social structure). Although civilization undergoes certain changes as a result of certain external and internal influences, its inner core remains unchanged. This approach to civilization is reflected in the theory of its cultural-historical types. Cultural-historical types are understood as societies with a defined territory and characteristics of cultural-social development [7, p. 65].

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the effectiveness of research in any field of science and the methodology for achieving the stated goal are of great importance in the study of scientific

fields. The correct approach to the study of science results in scientific innovations that can have a positive impact on the development of society. In this regard, we can see from history that the correct choice of methodological approaches is important when studying areas of science related to the national values of the people. As a result of the reforms carried out in the study of history after Uzbekistan gained independence, historical science in Uzbekistan has taken its place in world civilization based on new views and approaches.

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